

under natural light. Thylakoid protein was analyzed according to Aoki et al (1995).

The mutant plants produced expanded green leaves under 30-24 °C, fine-striped leaves under 25-19 °C, and white leaves under 20-14 °C (Fig. 1). After a shift in temperature the mutants often had expanded nonhomogeneously colored leaves. In some plants transferred from 30 to 20-14 °C, the upper parts of the leaf blades were green and the basal parts were white. However, in some plants transferred from 20-14 to 30-24 °C, the upper leaf parts were white and the basal parts were green. Leaf color of the mutant became faint with low temperature. In the polypeptide patterns of the thylakoid protein in the fine-striped and white leaves, some bands were missing or faint while others were added or intensified when compared with those in normal green leaves (Fig. 2).

The plastids in the leaf tip were observed to mature earlier than those in the basal region (Robertson and Laetsch 1974). Therefore, it seems that low temperature only affects the plastids of the mutant in the developmental stage. It is possible that a light-harvesting protein was lost in fine-striped and white leaves because about 23-kDa bands were lacking.

The mutant might be the result of a few nuclear gene mutations having been obtained by chronic δ -ray irradiation. We need to analyze the genes of the mutant.

Cited references

- Aoki C, Wada T, Nishimura T, Hattori K. 1995. Characterization and inheritance of variegated-leaf mutant in *Petunia hybrida*. *Breed. Sci.* 45:31-35.
- Robertson D, Laetsch WM. 1974. Structure and function of developing barley plastids. *Plant Physiol.* 54:148-159. ■

Cold tolerance at booting stage of highly cold-tolerant rice lines derived from a javanica and a japonica

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Norin PL 8 is a cold-tolerant rice variety derived from a javanica (Silewah) and a japonica (Hokkai 241). Highly cold-tolerant lines have been selected from crosses between different japonica rice cultivars at Tohoku (Fig. 1).

We compared cold tolerance at the booting stage of these lines (see table) through cold water treatment. The experiment was conducted in both 4-liter pots and in the ricefield. In the pot experiment, 20 seeds/pot for Norin PL8 were seeded on

16 May and six other lines were seeded in a box on 25 Apr.

Cold water (18.8 °C) treatment began on 13 Jul and ended at heading date for the lines. Seedlings that were raised in a box were transplanted on 26 May, with cold water treatment (18.8 °C) beginning on 27 Jun and ending 1 Sep. Water depth was 35 cm for both.

In the field experiment, Norin PL8 was seeded on 4 May and 13 May and two other lines were seeded on 27 Mar and 8 Apr. Water depth was 15 cm, and water temperature was 19.0 °C.

Both 90C2013 and Chubo 59 showed seed fertilities higher than that of Norin PL 8 (Fig. 2).

Results suggest that we can select highly cold-tolerant lines equal to that of javanica rice only from japonica rice. Accumulation of cold tolerance genes between javanica and japonica rices is possible. ■

1. Pedigrees of rice varieties used in the experiment.

2. Seed fertility of highly cold-tolerant lines treated with cold water in the pot experiment (18.8 °C) (a) and in the field experiment (19.0 °C) (b).